

Serbian Association for Cancer Research

**5th CONGRESS OF SDIR:
TRANSLATIONAL POTENTIAL OF
CANCER RESEARCH IN SERBIA**

**ABSTRACT
BOOK**

**Virtual event
December 3**

2021

**EACR
sponsored**

THE FIFTH CONGRESS OF THE SERBIAN ASSOCIATION FOR CANCER RESEARCH

with international participation
"TRANSLATIONAL POTENTIAL OF CANCER RESEARCH IN
SERBIA "

December 3, 2021, Virtual event
Serbian Association for Cancer Research (SDIR) is a member of the European Association for
Cancer Research (EACR).
President of SDIR-5 Congress
dr sc. med. Mirjana Branković-Magić

THE FIFTH CONGRESS OF THE SERBIAN ASSOCIATION FOR CANCER RESEARCH
with international participation "Translational potential of cancer research in Serbia" Virtual event,

December 3, 2021

Publisher: Srpsko društvo istraživača raka, 11000 Beograd
Year: 2021.

Editors: *dr sc. Marija Đorđić Crnogorac, dr sc. Milica
Nedeljković*

Print: Srpsko društvo istraživača raka, Beograd

Number of copies: 20

ISBN: 978-86-919183-3-0.

CIP - Каталогизacija u publikaciji - Narodna biblioteka Srbije,
Beograd

616-006(048)(0.034.2)

SERBIAN Association for Cancer Research. Congress (5 ; 2021)
Translational Potential of Cancer Research in Serbia [Elektronski izvor] :
abstract book / 5th Congress of the Serbian Association for Cancer
Research with International Participation SDIR-5, Virtual event, December
3, 2021 ; [editors Marija Đorđić Crnogorac, Milica Nedeljković]. – Beograd
: Srpsko društvo istraživača raka, 2021 (Beograd : Srpsko društvo
istraživača raka). - 1 elektronski optički disk (CD-ROM) ; 12 cm

Sistemski zahtevi: Nisu navedeni. - Nasl. sa naslovne strane dokumenta. -

Tiraž 20.

ISBN 978-86-919183-3-0

a) Онкологија - Апстракти

COBISS.SR-ID 52655625

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Quality of life in patients surgically treated for oral carcinoma

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Background: Most oral planocellular carcinomas are diagnosed in the late stages, which significantly reduces the chances of survival and impairs quality of life. This study examined quality of life in patients who were surgically treated. **Patients and Methods:** The study included patients surgically treated over a 3-year period (2014-2016). Data on patients, tumor type and localization, TNM classification, type of surgical intervention, and time since surgery were collected from the medical records. Post-surgery functional and aesthetic results were evaluated using the adapted University of Washington Quality of Life questionnaire. **Results:** Forty patients were included in the study. Male patients were more prevalent (27 vs 13) ($\chi^2=4.225$, $p<0.05$). Ratio of planocellular vs adenocarcinoma was 7:1 ($\chi^2=11.404$, $p=0.0007$). Osteotomy was performed in 52.5% of patients, and surgical intervention in the soft tissue in 47.5%. Compared to patients evaluated <1 year after surgery, patients who had been recovering >1 year showed better mood ($p=0.036$), functions of speech ($p=0.008$) and chewing ($p=0.04$), as well as patients who had soft tissue surgery (chewing: $p=0.016$; speech: $p=0.043$). Patients with T1 stage tumors considered their looks less disfigured and had fewer problems in appearing in public, compared with patients with T3 and T4 stage (CI – 95%). Interest in sex was significantly diminished in patients older than 30 years ($p=0.013$). **Conclusion:** The stage of disease, range of resection and success of reconstruction were decisive parameters for postoperative quality of life. Early detection of disease is of utmost importance for both survival and quality of life of patients with carcinoma.

Keywords: Oral cancer, quality of life, postoperative period

